
Four timeless principles of success

The legacy of my great-grandfather Mohamed Said Kamoun lives on. His principles transcend generations and serve as guiding lights for anyone seeking success, whether in business or personal life.

A recent trip to Tunis, filled with [the flavors of fresh, authentic Tunisian cuisine](#), gifted me with a journey into my family's past. My cousin, [Maher Kamoun](#), meticulously compiled a book chronicling the life of our great-grandfather. In April 2023, he launched this book in the vibrant atmosphere of [Espace Zmorda](#), a well-being space founded 15 years ago by [my sister Chiraz Khrouf and my mother Khadija Lasram](#).

[Mohamed Said Kamoun: Deep roots and branches of distinction—A book by Maher Kamoun.](#)

As I leafed through the pages, I found myself immersed in the remarkable life of [Mohamed Said Kamoun \(1868–1945\)](#), an individual whose legacy had been sporadically shared during our family gatherings. Although he passed away two decades before my birth, I discovered that his influence and principles had greatly shaped my upbringing. He was an esteemed entrepreneur whose footsteps have guided generations. His achievements in the olive oil industry, resulting in prestigious accolades and medals at agricultural expos in France during the early 20th century, were legendary within our family.

M. Said Kamoun’s medals for his olive oil at agricultural expos in France: 1911 Bronze medal in Roubaix and 1924 Gold medal in Paris. [Source: Maher Kamoun.](#)

However, as I read on, I realized that his real legacy extended beyond commercial success. It was encapsulated in four timeless principles that he ardently upheld—principles that served as his compass in business and life. These principles, which influenced my upbringing and have guided his numerous descendants through our ventures, continue to inspire us to this day.

The four principles hold universal significance and remain relevant in various contexts. Let’s explore them:

1—Diversify Activities

This first principle speaks to the wisdom of not putting all your eggs in one basket. It underscores the necessity of diversification, a lesson Said Kamoun learned from his foray into the olive oil business. By broadening his horizons, he managed to weather any crisis or poor harvest. Diversification was his hedge against unpredictability. This principle is as relevant today as it was then, reminding us to avoid complacency and to continuously seek diverse avenues for growth and security.

2—Monitor Market Trends

Said Kamoun was a keen observer and always kept his finger on the pulse of the market. He realized that understanding supply and demand dynamics, quantities, and pricing trends were crucial to success. It was his ability to read and adapt to market shifts that allowed him to stay ahead of the competition. For us today, in an era of rapid technological and societal changes, this principle of vigilance and adaptability is more pertinent than ever.

3—Honor Your Commitments

No measure of success can compensate for a lack of integrity. Said Kamoun was not only a successful businessman but also a respected individual. He attributed this respect to his unwavering commitment to honoring his word, whether it was a business contract or a personal promise. This principle serves as a reminder that the foundation of any enduring success is trust and credibility.

4—Help Others

The final principle reflects Said Kamoun’s humanistic approach to life and business. He believed in the power of helping others, seeing his success as a means to make a difference in the community. It was this principle that defined him more than his business achievements. It’s a timeless lesson on the value of empathy and compassion, reminding us that true success is not just about personal gains but also about uplifting others.

In conclusion, the story of Mohamed Said Kamoun is not just about a man who excelled in his trade; it’s about a person who lived his life on principles that go beyond commerce. These four principles of diversification, market vigilance, honoring commitments, and helping others stand the test of time. They serve as guiding lights for anyone seeking success, whether in business or personal life. They are a part of the legacy he left behind, a legacy that continues to inspire and guide his descendants, including me, and perhaps will inspire you as well.

[Basking in the glory of M. Said Kamoun’s award-winning olive oil, crafted from the majestic Chemlali olive trees of Sfax.](#)

[Book launch at Espace Zmorda, Soukra, Tunis.](#)

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